

USE OF ALGEBRAIC SYMMETRIC RECURRENCE AS A SUBSTITUTE FOR CAUCHY'S FORWARD-BACKWARD INDUCTION

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ABSTRACT. This work introduces an algebraic substitute for Augustin-Louis Cauchy's forward-backward induction for some well-known inequalities.

1. INTRODUCTION

This work introduces a substitute for Augustin-Louis Cauchy's classical proof of the arithmetic-geometric mean (AM-GM) inequality as presented in his 'Cours d'analyse de l'École Royale Polytechnique'. While replacing Cauchy's forward-backward induction with a recurrence-based argument, it retains and systematizes the nested symmetric algebraic structure that underlies the latter part of his original development. Section 2 describes the substitute method. This symmetry-based approach extends naturally to other canonical inequalities, including Jensen's, Minkowski's, and via mild algebraic elaboration, Hölder's inequality. Section 3 describes application of the method to this latter inequality.

2. APPLICATION TO AM-GM INEQUALITY

Theorem. For any positive integer n and any positive real numbers a_1, a_2, \dots, a_n ,

$$\frac{\sum_{k=1}^n a_k}{n} \geq \sqrt[n]{\prod_{k=1}^n a_k}$$

and equality holds when all n terms are equal.

Proof. Let $P(n)$ be the statement $\frac{\sum_{k=1}^n a_k}{n} \geq \sqrt[n]{\prod_{k=1}^n a_k}$ and its equality condition. We'll induct on n .

Induction base cases: $\frac{\sum_{k=1}^1 a_k}{1} = a_1 = \sqrt[1]{\prod_{k=1}^1 a_k}$, so $P(1)$ is trivially true.

Since $(\sqrt{a_1} - \sqrt{a_2})^2 \geq 0 \Leftrightarrow \frac{a_1 + a_2}{2} \geq \sqrt{a_1 a_2}$ where equality holds when $a_1 = a_2$, $P(2)$, namely

$$\frac{\sum_{k=1}^2 a_k}{2} = \frac{a_1 + a_2}{2} \geq \sqrt{a_1 a_2} = \sqrt[2]{\prod_{k=1}^2 a_k}$$

holds true, too.

Induction hypothesis: Suppose $P(n)$ holds true for a positive integer such that $n > 1$.

Induction step: Let $\mu = \frac{\sum_{k=1}^n a_k}{n}$, $\alpha = a_{n+1} > 0$ and $M = \frac{\sum_{k=1}^{n+1} a_k}{n+1}$. Then

$$\begin{aligned}
 M &= \frac{\sum_{k=1}^{n+1} a_k}{n+1} \\
 &= \frac{\sum_{k=1}^n a_k + \alpha}{n+1} \\
 &= \frac{n \cdot \frac{\sum_{k=1}^n a_k}{n} + \alpha}{n+1} \\
 &= \frac{n\mu + \alpha}{n+1}
 \end{aligned}
 \tag{2.1}$$

Furthermore,

$$\begin{aligned}
 M &= \frac{n^2\mu + n\alpha}{n(n+1)} \\
 &= \frac{(n^2 - 1)\mu + (\mu + n\alpha)}{n(n+1)} \\
 &= \frac{(n-1)(n+1)\mu + (\mu + n\alpha)}{n(n+1)} \\
 &= \frac{(n-1)\mu + \frac{\mu + n\alpha}{n+1}}{n}
 \end{aligned}$$

By applying $P(n)$ to the latter equation, we get:

$$M \geq \sqrt[n]{\mu^{n-1} \left(\frac{\mu + n\alpha}{n+1} \right)}
 \tag{2.2}$$

Note that the second term in the n^{th} root on the right side of the latter inequality is the symmetric form of M we've derived in (2.1), with regards to μ and α .

Since each of n terms in the inequality (2.2) will remain positive if we swapped μ and α , we know the same inequality holds true for its symmetric form, namely

$$\frac{(\mu + n\alpha)}{n+1} \geq \sqrt[n]{\alpha^{n-1} \left(\frac{\alpha + n\mu}{n+1} \right)} = \sqrt[n]{\alpha^{n-1} M}$$

If we apply this to (2.2), we get

$$M \geq \sqrt[n]{\mu^{n-1} \left(\frac{\mu + n\alpha}{n+1} \right)} \geq \sqrt[n]{\mu^{n-1} \sqrt[n]{\alpha^{n-1} M}}
 \tag{2.3}$$

Since each side of the latter inequality is positive, we may raise both to n^{th} power:

$$M^{n^2} \geq \mu^{n(n-1)} \alpha^{n-1} M \rightarrow M^{(n-1)(n+1)} \geq \mu^{n(n-1)} \alpha^{n-1} \rightarrow M^{n+1} \geq \mu^n \alpha$$

Canceling powers by $(n-1)$ above is justified by $n > 1$. And by $P(n)$, we have $\mu^n \geq \prod_{k=1}^n a_k$, wherefore:

$$M^{n+1} \geq \mu^n \alpha \geq \left(\prod_{k=1}^n a_k \right) \alpha = \prod_{k=1}^{n+1} a_k$$

Or:

$$M \geq \sqrt[n+1]{\prod_{k=1}^{n+1} a_k}$$

If we substitute M for its original expression, this is equivalent to

$$\frac{\sum_{k=1}^{n+1} a_k}{n+1} \geq \sqrt[n+1]{\prod_{k=1}^{n+1} a_k}$$

And from the equality condition for $P(n)$, equality for $P(n+1)$ holds when $a_1 = a_2 = \dots = a_n = \mu = \frac{(\mu+n\alpha)}{n+1}$, i.e. when all $n+1$ terms are equal.

Conclusion: The proposition $P(n)$ holds for all positive integers n . \square

3. APPLICATION TO HÖLDER'S INEQUALITY

Lemma. For any (x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n) and (y_1, y_2, \dots, y_n) in \mathbb{R}^n and any positive integers m and n ,

$$\left(\sum_{k=1}^n |x_k| \right)^{\frac{m-1}{m}} \left(\sum_{k=1}^n |y_k| \right)^{\frac{1}{m}} \geq \sum_{k=1}^n |x_k|^{\frac{m-1}{m}} |y_k|^{\frac{1}{m}}$$

and equality holds when a constant μ satisfies $\mu = \frac{|x_k|}{|y_k|}$ for every k such that $1 \leq k \leq n$.

Proof. Let $P(m)$ be the Lemma's statement for m .

Induction base cases: For $m = 1$, Lemma's equality is

$$\left(\sum_{k=1}^n |x_k| \right)^{\frac{m-1}{m}} \left(\sum_{k=1}^n |y_k| \right)^{\frac{1}{m}} = \left(\sum_{k=1}^n |x_k| \right)^{\frac{1-1}{1}} \left(\sum_{k=1}^n |y_k| \right)^{\frac{1}{1}} = \sum_{k=1}^n |y_k| = \sum_{k=1}^n |x_k|^{\frac{1-1}{1}} |y_k|^{\frac{1}{1}} = \sum_{k=1}^n |x_k|^{\frac{m-1}{m}} |y_k|^{\frac{1}{m}}$$

This equality always holds, including when a constant μ satisfies $\mu = \frac{|x_k|}{|y_k|}$ for every k such that $1 \leq k \leq n$. Hence $P(1)$ holds true.

For $m = 2$, $P(m)$ is

$$\left(\sum_{k=1}^n |x_k| \right)^{\frac{1}{2}} \left(\sum_{k=1}^n |y_k| \right)^{\frac{1}{2}} \geq \sum_{k=1}^n |x_k|^{\frac{1}{2}} |y_k|^{\frac{1}{2}}$$

such that equality holds when a constant μ satisfies $\mu = \frac{|x_k|}{|y_k|}$ for any k such that $1 \leq k \leq n$.

This is identical to Cauchy-Schwarz's inequality, which can be justified by the following algebraic inequality:

$$\sum_{i=1}^n \sum_{j=1}^n \left(\sqrt{|x_i|} \sqrt{|y_j|} - \sqrt{|x_j|} \sqrt{|y_i|} \right)^2 \geq 0$$

Induction hypothesis: Suppose $P(m)$ holds true for a positive integer such that $m > 1$.

Induction step: Let $X = \sum_{k=1}^n |x_k|$, $Y = \sum_{k=1}^n |y_k|$ and $M = (\sum_{k=1}^n |x_k|)^{\frac{m}{m+1}} (\sum_{k=1}^n |y_k|)^{\frac{1}{m+1}}$. Then

$$\begin{aligned}
 M &= \left(\sum_{k=1}^n |x_k| \right)^{\frac{m}{m+1}} \left(\sum_{k=1}^n |y_k| \right)^{\frac{1}{m+1}} \\
 &= X^{\frac{m}{m+1}} Y^{\frac{1}{m+1}} \\
 &= X^{\frac{m^2}{m(m+1)}} Y^{\frac{1}{m+1}} \\
 &= X^{\frac{m^2-1}{m(m+1)}} X^{\frac{1}{m(m+1)}} Y^{\frac{m}{m(m+1)}} \\
 &= X^{\frac{(m-1)(m+1)}{m(m+1)}} \left\{ X^{\frac{1}{m+1}} Y^{\frac{m}{m+1}} \right\}^{\frac{1}{m}} \\
 (3.1) \quad &= X^{\frac{m-1}{m}} \left\{ X^{\frac{1}{m+1}} Y^{\frac{m}{m+1}} \right\}^{\frac{1}{m}}
 \end{aligned}$$

Note that the 2nd factor on the right side of the latter equality raised to $\frac{1}{m}$ is the symmetric form of M about X and Y . Thus we know the same equality holds true for its symmetric form, namely

$$X^{\frac{1}{m+1}} Y^{\frac{m}{m+1}} = Y^{\frac{m-1}{m}} M^{\frac{1}{m}}$$

If we put this in (3.1) we get:

$$\begin{aligned}
 M &= X^{\frac{m-1}{m}} \left\{ X^{\frac{1}{m+1}} Y^{\frac{m}{m+1}} \right\}^{\frac{1}{m}} \\
 (3.2) \quad &= X^{\frac{m-1}{m}} \left\{ Y^{\frac{m-1}{m}} M^{\frac{1}{m}} \right\}^{\frac{1}{m}}
 \end{aligned}$$

Let $Z = \sum_{k=1}^n |x_k|^{\frac{m}{m+1}} |y_k|^{\frac{1}{m+1}}$. We multiply both sides of the latter equality (3.2) by $\frac{Z^{\frac{1}{m^2}}}{M^{\frac{1}{m^2}}}$ and apply $P(m)$ repeatedly to get:

$$\begin{aligned}
 Z^{\frac{1}{m^2}} M^{\frac{m^2-1}{m^2}} &= X^{\frac{m-1}{m}} \left\{ Y^{\frac{m-1}{m}} Z^{\frac{1}{m}} \right\}^{\frac{1}{m}} \\
 &= X^{\frac{m-1}{m}} \left\{ \left(\sum_{k=1}^n |y_k| \right)^{\frac{m-1}{m}} \left(\sum_{k=1}^n |x_k|^{\frac{m}{m+1}} |y_k|^{\frac{1}{m+1}} \right)^{\frac{1}{m}} \right\}^{\frac{1}{m}} \\
 &\geq X^{\frac{m-1}{m}} \left\{ \sum_{k=1}^n |x_k|^{\frac{1}{m+1}} |y_k|^{\frac{m^2-1}{m(m+1)} + \frac{1}{m(m+1)}} \right\}^{\frac{1}{m}} \\
 &= \left(\sum_{k=1}^n |x_k| \right)^{\frac{m-1}{m}} \left\{ \sum_{k=1}^n |x_k|^{\frac{1}{m+1}} |y_k|^{\frac{m}{m+1}} \right\}^{\frac{1}{m}} \\
 &\geq \sum_{k=1}^n |x_k|^{\frac{m^2-1}{m(m+1)} + \frac{1}{m(m+1)}} |y_k|^{\frac{1}{m+1}} \\
 &= \sum_{k=1}^n |x_k|^{\frac{m}{m+1}} |y_k|^{\frac{1}{m+1}} \\
 (3.3) \quad &= Z
 \end{aligned}$$

We divide both sides of the latter inequality in (3.3) by $Z^{\frac{1}{m^2}}$ again to get:

$$M^{\frac{m^2-1}{m^2}} \geq Z^{\frac{m^2-1}{m^2}}$$

Since $m > 1$, the exponent on both sides of the above inequality, namely $\frac{m^2-1}{m} > 0$. Hence

$$(3.4) \quad M \geq Z$$

This is the inequality in our $P(m+1)$, and if we apply the equality condition in $P(m)$ to the derivation of (3.3), the condition for (3.4) is that, for every k such that $1 \leq k \leq n$, constants μ_1 and μ_2 satisfy:

$$\mu_1 = \frac{|x_k|^{\frac{m}{m+1}} |y_k|^{\frac{1}{m+1}}}{|y_k|} \quad \text{and} \quad \mu_2 = \frac{|x_k|^{\frac{1}{m+1}} |y_k|^{\frac{m}{m+1}}}{|x_k|}$$

In other words, that a constant μ satisfies, for every k such that $1 \leq k \leq n$:

$$\mu = \mu_1 = \mu_2^{-1} = \frac{|x_k|}{|y_k|}$$

Which is the equality condition in $P(m+1)$. Hence our $P(m+1)$ holds true.

Conclusion: $P(m)$ holds for all positive integers m . □

Theorem. Let (x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n) and (y_1, y_2, \dots, y_n) be vectors in \mathbb{R}^n . For any positive real numbers $p, q > 0$ satisfying $\frac{1}{p} + \frac{1}{q} = 1$, we have:

$$\left(\sum_{k=1}^n |x_k|^p \right)^{\frac{1}{p}} \left(\sum_{k=1}^n |y_k|^q \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} \geq \sum_{k=1}^n |x_k y_k|$$

And equality holds when a constant μ satisfies $\mu = \frac{|x_k|^p}{|y_k|^q}$ for every k such that $1 \leq k \leq n$.

Proof. Assume we have positive integers m and n , and that for every integer j such that $0 < j \leq m$, we have a vector $v_j = (x_1^{(j)}, x_2^{(j)}, \dots, x_n^{(j)})$ in \mathbb{R}^n . If, for each j from 1 to m , we apply $P(j)$ in our Lemma in turn, which will amount to a total of m times, we will get:

$$(3.5) \quad \prod_{j=1}^m \left(\sum_{k=1}^n |x_k^{(j)}| \right)^{\frac{1}{m}} \geq \sum_{k=1}^n \prod_{j=1}^m |x_k^{(j)}|^{\frac{1}{m}}$$

We can derive a special case of the above (3.5) in which some of our m vectors v_j 's are identical one to each other, yielding arbitrary unequal rational weights, as follows:

Assume we have l distinct rational weights such that $\sum_{i=1}^l w_i = \sum_{i=1}^l \frac{a_i}{m} = 1$, where m is the common denominator of w_i 's and each a_i is a positive integer. For every integer i such that $0 < i \leq l$, let us denote the respective vector associated with w_i by $v_i = (x_1^{(i)}, x_2^{(i)}, \dots, x_n^{(i)})$ in \mathbb{R}^n . Then we apply (3.5) to our vectors v_i 's, paying attention to using each v_i exactly for a_i times, for every integer i such that $0 < i \leq l$, to get:

$$(3.6) \quad \prod_{i=1}^l \left(\sum_{k=1}^n |x_k^{(i)}| \right)^{w_i} \geq \sum_{k=1}^n \prod_{i=1}^l |x_k^{(i)}|^{w_i}$$

This is the generalized version of Hölder's inequality for rational weights. Furthermore, \mathbb{Q} is dense in \mathbb{R} , hence we have, by continuity, the inequality (3.6) for arbitrary positive real weights. In particular, if we let, in (3.6), $l = 2$, $w_1 = \frac{1}{p}$ and $w_2 = \frac{1}{q}$ for positive real numbers p and q , and $v_1 = (|x_1|^p, |x_2|^p, \dots, |x_n|^p)$, $v_2 = (|y_1|^q, |y_2|^q, \dots, |y_n|^q)$, then we have:

$$\left(\sum_{k=1}^n |x_k|^p \right)^{\frac{1}{p}} \left(\sum_{k=1}^n |y_k|^q \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} \geq \sum_{k=1}^n |x_k y_k|$$

with $\frac{1}{p} + \frac{1}{q} = 1$, which is the inequality we intended to show in our theorem. \square